

High-rate ammonium removal and recovery and hydrogen production from wastewater using microbial electrolysis cell

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HIGHLIGHTS

- MEC efficiently removes and recovers ammonium from wastewater streams.
- NH_4^+ removal and recovery rate of 69.8 and 37.9 $\text{gN m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$ were achieved.
- MEC produces H_2 with 1557.6 $\text{L H}_2 \text{m}^{-3} \text{d}^{-1}$ and efficiency of $31.4 \pm 2.9 \text{ kWh kg}^{-1} \text{H}_2$.
- WW treatment of 1.2 $\text{kg COD m}^{-3} \text{d}^{-1}$ and efficiency of 0.11 $\text{kWh kg}^{-1} \text{COD}$ was achieved.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

This study presents an integrated approach combining microbial electrolysis cells (MECs) with three external ammonium extraction systems, Gas Diffuser (GD), Stripping Column (SP) and Thermally Assisted Stripping (SP + T), to enhance nitrogen removal and recovery from high-strength wastewater. Among the configurations, MECs operated at 0.75 V and integrated with SP + T achieved the highest performances, with current density of 8.8 A m^{-2} , ammonium removal and recovery rates reaching 69.8 and 37.9 $\text{gN m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$, Faradaic efficiency of 74.9 % and specific energy consumption for ammonium recovery of 3.3 $\text{kWh kg}^{-1} \text{N}$. The SP + T system boosted ammonia volatilization at the catholyte and accelerated ammonium transport across the cation exchange membrane, leading to improved removal and recovery performance. Concurrently, H_2 generation reached 1557.6 $\text{L H}_2 \text{m}^{-3} \text{d}^{-1}$ with specific energy consumption of 31.4 $\text{kWh kg}^{-1} \text{H}_2$. These results highlight that coupling MEC and SP + T is a promising configuration for efficient nitrogen recovery and renewable hydrogen generation, while demonstrating MECs as a sustainable technology for wastewater treatment and resource recovery.

Abbreviations: BEC, Bioelectrochemical Concentration Cell; BES, Bioelectrochemical System; CE, Coulombic Efficiency; CEM, Cation Exchange Membrane; COD, Chemical Oxygen Demand; FE, Faradaic Efficiency; GD, Gas Diffuser; MEC, Microbial Electrolysis Cell; MFC, Microbial Fuel Cell; PEMEL, Proton Exchanger Membrane Electrolyser; ORR, Organic Removal Rate; SEC, Specific Energy Consumption; SP, Stripping; SP+T, Thermally assisted MEC stripping; STR, Surface Treatment Rate; WW, Wastewater; WWTP, Wastewater Treatment Plant.

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Structured abstract: The study presents a novel approach for enhancing nitrogen recovery from wastewater using MECs integrated with different ammonium stripping systems. By evaluating three configurations, gas diffuser (GD), ambient-temperature stripping (SP) and thermally assisted MEC stripping system (SP + T), this work systematically investigates how operational strategies affect the performance of nitrogen removal and recovery. Key performance indicators such as current density, Faradaic efficiency, specific energy consumption and hydrogen production are quantified and compared as well. Furthermore, organic removal rates, percentage and energy efficiency of organic matter treatment in the anode are also assessed. The findings described highlight the importance of optimizing operational parameters such as temperature and contact surface to maximize ammonium recovery in MECs. The SP + T approach is relevant for bioelectrochemical and wastewater treatment systems aiming to optimize nitrogen management and valorization. Furthermore, the study includes a comprehensive energy analysis and contextualizes the results with respect to conventional ammonia production technologies such as the Haber–Bosch process, among others. Thus, these results are of relevance to the fields of wastewater treatment, nutrient recovery, energy/hydrogen production, environmental biotechnology and circular economy, offering a scalable and energy-efficient solution for nutrient valorization.

1. Introduction

Nitrogen is a fundamental element in biological systems, playing a crucial role in the biochemical cycles of ecosystems and industrial applications such as agriculture. However, excessive nitrogen discharge into the environment, primarily in the form of ammonium (NH_4^+), nitrate (NO_3^-) and nitrite (NO_2^-), has led to severe environmental threats, including eutrophication of water bodies, groundwater contamination and the emission of greenhouse gases such as nitrous oxide (N_2O).

Over 81 % of global ammonia emissions come from agricultural activities, primary in form of wastewater. (Wyer et al., 2022). In wastewater treatment plants, nitrogen is typically removed by biological processes such as nitrification–denitrification, autotrophic anaerobic ammonium oxidation (anammox), etc. (Zhang and Liu, 2021). Although widely implemented, these methods focus primarily on nitrogen elimination rather than recovery and are associated with high energy demands. Other treatment technologies, such as air stripping, membrane separation, reverse osmosis, electrochemical, electro dialysis, chemical precipitation of struvite, or adsorption in zeolites, allow ammonium removal and recovery in a circular approach (Zhang and Liu, 2021). However, these technologies are only cost-effective at ammonium concentrations exceeding $2 \text{ g NH}_4^+ \text{ L}^{-1}$ (Cruz et al., 2019). Globally, around 20 million tons of ammonium are embedded in wastewater annually, representing 15–19 % of global nitrogen demand as a fertilizer. This demand is mainly produced by Haber-Bosch process (Cruz et al., 2019; Qadir et al., 2020). Although, Haber-Bosch process is a mature and highly optimized technology operating near its thermodynamic limits, it remains energy-intensive (Erfani et al., 2024).

Various bioelectrochemical systems, including microbial fuel cells (MFCs), microbial electrolysis cells (MECs) and bioelectroconcentration cells (BECs), offer a promising alternative, enabling simultaneous nitrogen removal and recovery with lower energy input (Koskue et al., 2021; Lee et al., 2022; Losantos et al., 2021; Rodríguez Arredondo et al., 2015; Ul et al., 2024). In MECs, electroactive bacteria (EAB) oxidize organic matter at the anode, releasing electrons that drive reduction reactions at the cathode, such as hydrogen evolution reaction (HER), producing hydrogen and hydroxyls productions. Ionic exchange membranes maintain electroneutrality between chambers (Dattatraya Saratale et al., 2022). Driven by the electrochemical gradient, NH_4^+ migrates from the anode to the cathode via cation exchange membranes. In the cathode chamber, the basic pH resulting from the HER promotes the conversion of NH_4^+ to NH_3 , enabling gas-phase recovery. Compared to conventional methods, MECs consume less energy and simultaneously remove organic matter, enhancing overall treatment efficiency. Coupling MECs with stripping systems further improves nitrogen recovery by shifting the $\text{NH}_4^+/\text{NH}_3$ equilibrium and capturing NH_3 in acid traps as ammonium sulfate, ammonium chloride and ammonium nitrate (Rodríguez Arredondo et al., 2015; Ul et al., 2024; Galeano et al., 2023). Reported ammonium recovery efficiencies range from 31 % to 94.3 % with recovery rates reaching up to $70 \text{ g N m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$ in synthetic media

containing $2.5 \text{ g L}^{-1} \text{ NH}_4^+$, using a double-chamber MEC reactors (Carucci et al., 2022). Energy consumption is a key parameter, with MECs requiring between 1 and 27 kWh kgN^{-1} for nitrogen recovery (Zamora et al., 2017), which is lower than the conventional NH_4^+ removal technologies, such as the nitrification–denitrification process (13 kWh kgN^{-1}), the Anammox process (5 kWh kgN^{-1}) and removal ammonia stripping (9 kWh kgN^{-1}) or Haber-Bosch for ammonia production ($8.6 \text{ kWh kgNH}_3^{-1}$) (Carucci et al., 2022; Erfani et al., 2024).

MEC systems studied for nitrogen removal and recovery, also enable H_2 production at the cathode. Although H_2 generation has been reported in only a few studies focused on nitrogen recovery, notable results include a production rate of $48.6 \text{ m}^3 \text{ H}_2 \text{ m}^{-3} \text{ d}^{-1}$ are reported by Kuntke et al. (Kuntke et al., 2014). Compared to technologies such as proton exchange membrane electrolyzers (PEMEL), which operate at current densities of $6000\text{--}20,000 \text{ A m}^{-2}$ (El-Shafie, 2023; Sezer et al., 2025), MECs require substantially lower current density, $1\text{--}15 \text{ A m}^{-2}$. This lower current demand limits H_2 production rates, yet MECs have promising results at laboratory scale, achieving $1\text{--}10 \text{ m}^3 \text{ H}_2 \text{ m}^{-3} \text{ reactor and day}^{-1}$. However, performance drops significantly under real wastewater conditions at industrially relevant scales, with rates below $0.1 \text{ m}^3 \text{ H}_2 \text{ m}^{-3} \text{ d}^{-1}$ (Guerrero-Sodric et al., 2023; Park et al., 2022).

Despite these limitations, MECs employ wastewater at the anode, avoiding the use of high-purity water and enabling treatment of wastewater through oxidizing organic matter. Thus, the anodic oxidation of acetate ($E'_0 = -0.28 \text{ V vs. SHE}$) is coupled with the cathodic HER ($E'_0 = -0.41 \text{ V vs. SHE}$). This results in a theoretical cell voltage of -0.13 V , which means that an external power input is required. In contrast, conventional electrolyzers, which oxidize water at the anode ($E'_0 = 0.82 \text{ V vs. SHE}$), require a theoretical cell voltage of -1.23 V , implying higher energy input (Rabaey and Rozendal, 2010). Considering all overpotentials, MECs can operate at applied voltages of $0.75\text{--}1.25 \text{ V}$, enabling H_2 production with specific electricity consumption below $35 \text{ kWh kg}^{-1} \text{ H}_2$ (Pérez-Pi et al., 2024), compared to over $55 \text{ kWh kg}^{-1} \text{ H}_2$ required by electrolyzers.

This research introduces a novel approach to boost nitrogen recovery from wastewater using microbial electrolysis cells (MECs) integrated with three ammonium stripping strategies. By assessing these configurations, the study reveals how operational parameters directly impact nitrogen removal and recovery efficiency. Key metrics such as current density, Faradaic efficiency, energy consumption, hydrogen production rates and organic matter removal are quantified and benchmarked. The energy analysis positions this approach as an energy-efficient alternative to conventional ammonia production methods.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. MEC setup

A flat-plate, double-chamber MEC reactor was utilized. The effective area of the reactor is 100 cm^2 ($10 \times 10 \text{ cm}$) and the internal volume of

anode chamber was of 200 mL and cathode chamber was 150 mL. A cationic exchange membrane (CEM) had an effective area of 100 cm² (RALEX CMHPP, from MEGA, Prague, Czech Republic) and divided the two chambers. The anode was a 100 cm² carbon felt (Sigracell KFD 2.5 EA, from SGL Carbon, Wiesbaden, Germany), while the cathode was a 100 cm² carbon cloth with platinum on carbon catalyst (0.5 mg cm⁻² 60 % wt.% Pt on Vulcan cloth electrode, FuelCellStore, Bryan, TX, USA). Anode and cathode had a current collector made of stainless steel 316L. Peristaltic pumps (HygiaFlex HF-LabV1) were used to recirculate the electrolytes at flow rate of 200 mL min⁻¹. Also, in some cycles auxiliary buffer tanks of 200 and 800 mL were used to increase the working volume of anolyte and catholyte solutions, respectively. The anolyte contained 3 g/L of N-NH₄⁺ and its composition was: NaHCO₃ (1.5 g L⁻¹), K₂HPO₄ (0.3 g L⁻¹), MgSO₄ (0.1 g L⁻¹), CaCl₂ (0.05 g L⁻¹), NH₄HCO₃ (14.37 g L⁻¹) and NH₄CH₃COO (2.5 g L⁻¹), with a pH of 8.3 and conductivity of 19.6 mS cm⁻¹. The catholyte was composed by the same electrolyte, but without NH₄HCO₃ nor NH₄CH₃COO with an initial pH around 9.3 and conductivity around 4 mS cm⁻¹.

A nitrogen extraction system was externally coupled to the MEC reactor (Fig. 1). Three different systems were tested sequentially: 1) gas diffuser (GD), 2) stripping column (SP) and 3) stripping column with the MEC reactor operated at 30 °C and without the cathode tank (SP + T) (Fig. 1). The GD configuration consists of a 500 mL bottle with an inlet gas tube connected to a micro filter candle (Duran, Germany), used to bubble the NH₃-rich gas from the catholyte headspace. The gas from the bottle headspace is then used to strip NH₃ from the catholyte. The SP configuration consists of a homemade stripping column made from a methacrylate tube (internal diameter: 3 cm, length: 38.5 cm) with connections at the top and bottom. The column is filled with glass rings (5 mm diameter, 5 mm length, 3 mm hole diameter). The NH₃-rich gas is bubbled into the bottom of the column and the gas from the column headspace is used to strip NH₃ from the catholyte. In the SP + T configuration, there is no cathode buffer tank and the stripping gas is directly recirculated to the cathode chamber.

The extraction solution in all the operated modes was H₂SO₄ (0.25 M). The gas from the cathode headspace is bubbled into the H₂SO₄ extraction tank and the headspace gas from this tank, free of NH₃, is recirculated into the bottom part of the catholyte to strip NH₃. This gas is circulated using a peristaltic pump (HygiaFlex HF-LabV1) at a flow rate of 200 mL min⁻¹. A total of 12 batch cycles were considered for this study, the GD condition corresponds to cycle 1 and 2, SP condition to cycle 3 to 6 and SP + T condition to cycle 7 to 12. Table S 1 shows the specific conditions of each batch.

Fig. 1. Scheme of laboratory setup, for SP configuration, for NH₄⁺ removal and recovery.

2.2. MEC operation

The MEC reactor was operated at room temperature (in case of GD and SP) and at 30 °C (in case of SP + T), applying a cell voltage of 0.75 V. The reactor was maintained at atmospheric pressure during all tests. All electrochemical tests were made with Bio-Logic VMP3 potentiostat/galvanostat (BioLogic, Grenoble, France).

2.3. Analytical characterization

Liquid samples were taken periodically from anolyte, catholyte and extracting solution. Electric conductivity and pH were monitored using a multimeter HQ40D (Hach Lange, Spain) with probes CDC401 and PHC101, respectively. Chemical oxygen demand, COD and N-NH₄⁺ determinations were carried out using LCK series kits (Hach Lange, Spain). Gas samples were analyzed by gas chromatography using a MicroGC 490-TCD (Agilent Technologies, Spain). The gas produced in the cathode is collected in a Tedlar sampling bag placed on top of the stripping system in SP-based configurations and on top of the catholyte tank in GD-based configuration. The gas is collected throughout the entire cycle. Subsequently, gas composition is analyzed using a gas chromatograph (GC Agilent 490, Spain) and the gas volume is measured with a gas-tight syringe.

2.4. Calculations

Nitrogen removal and recovery rates and efficiencies are obtained as follows:

$$\text{N-NH}_4^+ \text{ Removal Rate (gN}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{d)} = \frac{gN_i(\text{anolyte}) - gN_f(\text{anolyte})}{A_{\text{membrane}}(\text{m}^2) \cdot t(\text{d})} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{N-NH}_4^+ \text{ Recovery Rate (gN}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{d)} = \frac{gN_f(\text{extraction sol.})}{A_{\text{membrane}}(\text{m}^2) \cdot t(\text{d})} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{N-NH}_4^+ \text{ Removal Eff. (%) = } \frac{gN_i(\text{anolyte}) - gN_f(\text{anolyte})}{gN_i(\text{anolyte})} \cdot 100 \quad (3)$$

$$\text{N recovered vs N removed (%) = } \frac{gN_f(\text{extraction sol.})}{gN_i(\text{anolyte}) - gN_f(\text{anolyte})} \cdot 100 \quad (4)$$

where $gN_i(\text{anolyte})$ is the initial nitrogen mass contained in the anolyte, $gN_f(\text{anolyte})$ is the final nitrogen mass contained in anolyte, $gN_f(\text{extraction sol.})$ is the final nitrogen mass contained in extraction solution (H₂SO₄ tank), A_{membrane} is the area of the membrane (100 cm²) and t is the duration of cycle.

The Specific Energy Consumption for kilogram of nitrogen removed or recovered, SEC_N , is calculated as follows:

$$SEC_N (\text{kWh kg}^{-1} \text{N}) = \frac{I \cdot V \cdot t}{mN \cdot 1000} \quad (5)$$

where the mN is the mass of nitrogen removed or recovered as $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$, I is the electric current intensity and V is the cell voltage applied (0.75 V).

Faradaic efficiency regarding the N-NH_4^+ transference from anolyte to catholyte chamber throughout the cationic exchange membrane is calculated as follows:

$$\text{N-NH}_4^+ \text{ FE} (\%) = \frac{n_{\text{NH}_4^+} \cdot F}{I \cdot t} \cdot 100 \quad (6)$$

where $n_{\text{NH}_4^+}$ is the number of NH_4^+ moles that are removed from the water feed of anolyte chamber and F is Faraday constant.

The cathode efficiency of MEC reactor is evaluated assuming that there is only one reduction reaction (no other secondary reactions that consume the energy demanded by the system are observed), which is the HER, theoretical H_2 produced is given by the following formula:

$$\text{H}_2 \text{ theor. (mols H}_2) = \frac{I \cdot t}{F \cdot e^-} \quad (7)$$

where e^- is the number of electrons involved in the reaction (two).

The energy efficiency has been evaluated considering just the energy input demanded by the reactor itself; that means the contribution of all the peripherals, as peristaltic pumps and external heating system, is not included. This efficiency has been expressed as the Specific Energy Consumption, SEC_{H_2} , required for H_2 produced:

$$SEC_{\text{H}_2} (\text{kWh kg}^{-1} \text{H}_2) = \frac{I \cdot V \cdot t}{mH_2 (\text{kg})} \quad (8)$$

where mH_2 is the mass of H_2 calculated from gas volume obtained and concentration of H_2 in the gas.

The H_2 theoretical production rate is determined by the following equation:

$$\text{Theor. H}_2 \text{ prod. rate (L H}_2 \text{ prod m}^{-3} \text{ d}^{-1}) = \frac{H_2 \text{ theor.}}{V_{\text{react}} \cdot t} \quad (9)$$

where the V_{react} is the volume of the cathode 0.4 L.

Faradaic efficiency regarding the H_2 production in the cathode chamber is calculated as follows:

$$\text{Cat FE} (\%) = \frac{mH_2}{mH_2 \text{ theor.}} \cdot 100 \quad (10)$$

where the mH_2 is the H_2 mass calculated from the gas volume obtained and concentration of H_2 in the gas and $mH_2 \text{ theor.}$ is the theoretical H_2 mass that can be produced considering the total current demand, calculated with Eq. (1).

The Specific Energy Consumption for kilogram of COD removed, SEC_{COD} , is calculated as follows:

$$SEC_{\text{COD}} (\text{kWh kg}^{-1} \text{COD}) = \frac{I \cdot V \cdot t}{\Delta \text{COD}} \quad (11)$$

where the ΔCOD is the balance of COD mass between the start and end of the cycle.

The organic removal rate (ORR) is the mass of COD that the MEC is available to degrade per unit of anodic volume and time.

$$\text{ORR (kgCOD m}^{-3} \text{ d}^{-1}) = \frac{\Delta \text{COD}}{V_{\text{an}} \cdot t} \quad (12)$$

where V_{an} is the volume of anode (1 L).

Anodic Coulombic efficiency (An CE) is the relationship between the

electrons collected in the anode, which are related to the electrical current demand of the MEC and the total electrons generated considering the COD degraded:

$$\text{An CE} (\%) = \frac{MO_2 I t}{F b V_{\text{an}} \Delta \text{COD}} \cdot 100 \quad (13)$$

where M is the molecular weight of oxygen, b is the number of electrons exchanged per mole of oxygen (four).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. System operation for ammonium removal and recovery

The electrochemical performance of MEC was assessed under the three different operational modes, GD, SP and SP + T. Table 1 presents the current density, anode potential and cathode potential of the MEC operated under an applied voltage of 0.75 V. The highest current density ($8.8 \pm 0.7 \text{ A m}^{-2}$) was observed in the SP + T mode, suggesting that temperature enhancement facilitates electron transfer and improves the overall bioelectrochemical activity of the MEC, especially of the anode (Oliot et al., 2017; Zhang et al., 2019). No significant difference was observed between the current densities of the GD and SP modes (6.3 ± 0.9 and $5.7 \pm 0.6 \text{ A m}^{-2}$, respectively), as both configurations employed the same MEC reactor operating at ambient temperature. Current density–time curves for the three conditions (Fig. S 1) also demonstrate an increase in current density under the SP + T configuration, while the chronoamperometric profiles of GD and SP are similar. This reinforces the conclusion that temperature enhances electron transfer and the overall electrochemical performance of the MEC, as reported in the mentioned references.

The current density demand in each mode influenced the electrodes potential. The SP + T mode exhibited the most positive anode potential ($-241.8 \pm 28.6 \text{ mV}$), which is expected given the increased current demand, causing the anode potential to shift toward more positive values. In contrast, the SP mode, which required the lowest current density, allowed the anode potential to remain more negative, approaching open circuit conditions (Nam et al., 2011; Rousseau et al., 2020). Regarding the cathode potential, the SP + T exhibited the least negative value ($-990.7 \pm 36.2 \text{ mV}$), indicating a lower overpotential for the HER due to the temperature effect (Guerrero-Sodric et al., 2023; Kyazze et al., 2010; Wang et al., 2017). These findings highlight that temperature-assisted operation enhances MEC performance by increasing current density, reaction rate, mass transport and decreasing overpotential making it a promising strategy for optimizing bioelectrochemical processes.

Fig. 2 presents the N-NH_4^+ removal and recovery rates under different experimental conditions: GD, SP and SP + T. The highest N-NH_4^+ removal rate from the anolyte solution was observed in the SP + T condition, reaching $69.8 \pm 6.5 \text{ gN m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$. This represents a 22 % increase compared to the GD ($57.0 \pm 10.8 \text{ gN m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$) and a 30 % increase relative to the SP system at ambient temperature ($53.8 \pm 10.4 \text{ gN m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$). These results suggest that integrating stripping with MEC operated at 30°C enhances nitrogen removal. This improvement is likely attributed to the increased current density in MEC reactors operating at 30°C (8.8 A m^{-2} for SP + T compared to 6.3 and 5.7 A m^{-2} for GD and SP, respectively), which enhances cation migration, such as NH_4^+ , from the anolyte to the catholyte chamber. In the cathode, the

Table 1

Electrochemical results of MEC operated with three conditions under applied cell voltage of 0.75 V.

Operation mode	J / A m^{-2}	E_{anode} / mV	E_{cathode} / mV
Gas Diffuser	6.3 ± 0.9	-344.5 ± 31.8	-1084 ± 38.2
Stripping	5.7 ± 0.6	-382 ± 20.8	-1125.5 ± 21.2
Stripping + T	8.8 ± 0.7	-241.8 ± 28.6	-990.7 ± 36.2

Fig. 2. NH_4^+ removal (orange bar) and recovery (blue with white dotted bar) rates of MEC operated at 0.75 V with GD, SP and SP + T conditions. GD: gas diffuser; SP: stripping column; SP + T: stripping column with MEC operated at 30 °C.

higher current density achieved by the SP + T configuration enhances the hydrogen evolution reaction, leading to an increase of hydroxide production rate. This facilitates the conversion of NH_4^+ to NH_3 . Additionally, the elevated temperature promotes NH_3 volatilization in the catholyte chamber, reducing NH_3 concentration and thereby facilitating the conversion of NH_4^+ to NH_3 . This reduction in NH_3 concentration helps to maintain the chemical gradient, further enhancing the migration of NH_4^+ from the anolyte to the catholyte, contributing to improved anolyte's NH_4^+ removal rate.

Regarding N- NH_4^+ recovery, the SP + T approach also demonstrated the highest performance, with a recovery rate of $37.9 \pm 9.5 \text{ gN m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$. This value is approximately three times higher than that obtained with the stripping method ($12.7 \pm 2.2 \text{ gN m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$) and more than seven times higher than the gas diffuser system ($5.2 \pm 0.5 \text{ gN m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$). Also, in the case of the SP + T mode, the difference between ammonium removal and recovery rates is more balanced, as the increased temperature of the catholyte enhances ammonia volatilization from the cathode. This effect is well reported, as higher temperatures promote the transition of NH_4^+ to NH_3 gas, facilitating its extraction from the system (Jamaludin et al., 2018). Additionally, the SP mode demonstrates improved performance compared to the GD mode, despite both operating at ambient temperature. This improvement can be attributed to the significantly larger gas-liquid contact surface in the SP configuration, which enhances mass transfer and promotes more efficient NH_3 stripping. Considering that the pH values of the cathodic electrolytes are similar for the three conditions (11.4, 11.7 and 11.3, for GD, SP and SP + T respectively), the described findings highlight the importance of optimizing operational parameters such as temperature and contact surface to maximize NH_4^+ recovery in MEC. This approach could be particularly beneficial for bioelectrochemical and wastewater treatment systems aiming to optimize nitrogen management and valorization. Highlighting the importance of utilizing residual heat in wastewater treating and valorizing systems as a key strategy to improve nitrogen recovery by MECs. The SP + T configuration exhibited one of the highest N- NH_4^+ removal rates reported in the literature for BES, along with a remarkable recovery rate that approaches the upper range of values previously described (Galeano et al., 2023; Zamora et al., 2017). Furthermore, the removal rates achieved in this study are consistent with those reported by Ui et al. ($33 \text{ gN m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$) and Hou et al. ($36 \text{ gN m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$) (Hou et al., 2018; Ui et al., 2024), reinforcing the relevance and reliability of the observed performance. These results highlight the high efficiency and potential of the SP + T configuration for both NH_4^+ removal and recovery as $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$.

Fig. 3 presents the energy balance, expressed as SEC_N , for N- NH_4^+ removal and recovery under the three experimental conditions

Fig. 3. Specific Energy Consumption for removal (red bar) and recovery of N (white bar with yellow stripes) and % of N recovered respect to N removed (blue line) of MEC operated at 0.75 V with GD, SP and SP + T conditions. GD: gas diffuser; SP: stripping column; SP + T: stripping column with MEC operated at 30 °C.

evaluated. The SEC_N removal was comparable across all configurations: 2.0 ± 0.1 , 1.9 ± 0.3 and $2.3 \pm 0.3 \text{ kWh kg}^{-1} \text{ N}$ for GD, SP and SP + T, respectively. The similarity in SEC_N values between GD and SP is attributed to their comparable N- NH_4^+ removal rates and current densities demand. Although the SP + T configuration achieved a higher N- NH_4^+ removal rate, it also required a higher current density (higher energy). These two factors effectively balanced each other, resulting in a similar SEC_N to the other configurations.

In contrast, the SEC_N values for N- NH_4^+ recovery were significantly higher than those for N- NH_4^+ removal in both the GD and SP configurations, accounting for 21.8 ± 4.8 and $8.2 \pm 2.7 \text{ kWh kg}^{-1} \text{ N}$, respectively. This increase is primarily due to the low recovery efficiency in these systems, where only 10 % and 25 % of the N- NH_4^+ removed from the anolyte were recovered as $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ in the GD and SP configurations, respectively (Fig. 3). These low recovery efficiencies are also evident in the large differences observed between the N- NH_4^+ removal and N- NH_4^+ recovery rates shown in Fig. 2. In contrast, the SP + T configuration recovered 54.2 % of the N- NH_4^+ removed, more than twice the recovery efficiency of the SP configuration. This result highlights the positive influence of temperature on the NH_3 stripping efficiency in the catholyte. Consequently, the SEC_N recovery in the SP + T configuration was significantly lower, $3.3 \pm 1.8 \text{ kWh kg}^{-1} \text{ N}$. This value is among the lowest reported in the literature (Galeano et al., 2023; Zamora et al., 2017) and demonstrates high energy-efficiency potential when compared to the energy demand of the Haber-Bosch process, which consumes approximately $8.6 \text{ kWh kg}^{-1} \text{ NH}_3$ (Erfani et al., 2024).

Additionally, the SEC_N removal values in all three configurations were lower than those typically reported for conventional NH_4^+ removal technologies (Carucci et al., 2022), underscoring the potential of MEC, particularly coupling it with SP + T, as a promising and energy-efficient strategy for both NH_4^+ removal from wastewater and the production of ammonium-based fertilizers. It is worth noting that the thermal energy required to heat the system was not included in the SEC_N calculations. However, the system was operated at a temperature of 30 °C and in practical industrial applications, this heating demand could potentially be met using residual or waste heat streams in the treatment facility itself.

Table S4 and Figure S2 depict the nitrogen removal and recovery performance of the SP + T configuration over time for six batches conducted using this configuration. Together, these results indicate that, although some variations exist between cycles, nitrogen removal and recovery performance remained relatively stable across cycles without any clear trend. This demonstrates the stability and robustness of the system.

Table 2 presents the Faradaic efficiency (FE) of N- NH_4^+ , which

Table 2

Faradaic Efficiencies and COD removal performance parameters of MEC operated at 0.75 V with GD, SP and SP + T conditions. GD: gas diffuser; SP: stripping column; SP + T: stripping column with MEC operated at 30 °C.

Operation mode	N-NH ₄ ⁺ FE / %	An CE / %	Cat FE / %	COD _{rem} / %	ORR / kg _{COD} m ⁻³ d ⁻¹	SEC _{COD} / kWh kg _{COD} ⁻¹
GD	49.3 ± 5.2	67.6 ± 21.3	52.4 ± 1.7	52.1 ± 0.7	0.7 ± 0.1	0.17 ± 0.05
SP	41.7 ± 16.6	44.9 ± 2.5	59.1 ± 7.6	50.5 ± 2.2	0.9 ± 0.1	0.11 ± 0.01
SP + T	74.9 ± 17.0	59.0 ± 9.1	64.5 ± 5.9	58.1 ± 10.6	1.2 ± 0.1	0.13 ± 0.01

represents the molar ratio between the electrons transferred through the external circuit from anode to cathode and the moles of NH₄⁺ migrated across the cation exchange membrane (CEM). The GD and SP operational modes exhibited similar N-NH₄⁺ FE values, with 49.3 ± 5.2 % and 41.7 ± 16.6 %, respectively. In contrast, the SP + T mode led to a significant increase, achieving an N-NH₄⁺ FE of 74.9 ± 17.0 %. Operation at 30 °C (SP + T) contributes to this effect, potentially through the combined action of the following suggested mechanisms. Firstly, increased temperature promotes the stripping of NH₃ from the catholyte, thereby lowering its concentration and shifting the NH₄⁺/NH₃ equilibrium toward further NH₄⁺ deprotonation and migration. Meanwhile, other competing cations tend to accumulate in the cathode chamber, decreasing their concentration gradient across the membrane and potentially reducing their transport rate. Secondly, higher temperatures improve the kinetics of ion transport by decreasing membrane resistance and enhancing the diffusivity of NH₄⁺ through the CEM (Raka et al., 2021).

3.2. H₂ production performance

One of the key added values of N-NH₄⁺ removal and recovery using MEC technology is the simultaneous generation of H₂ in the cathodic chamber. A significant contribution of the present study lies in the quantification of H₂ production rates and specific energy consumption (SEC_{H₂}), parameters that are scarcely reported in the literature in conjunction with N-NH₄⁺ removal and recovery (Galeano et al., 2023).

As shown in Fig. 4 and Table S3, H₂ production rates were determined for three MEC configurations. H₂ production is expected to be directly proportional to the system's current density and accordingly, the measured H₂ production rates for the GD and SP configurations were comparable, reaching 902.7 ± 151.7 and 931.7 ± 213.8 LH₂ m⁻³ reactor d⁻¹, respectively, corresponding to current densities of 6.3 and 5.7 A m⁻² (Table 1). Although the GD configuration exhibited a slightly higher

Fig. 4. SEC for H₂ production (green bars) and H₂ production rate (grey line) of MEC operated at 0.75 V with GD, SP and SP + T conditions. GD: gas diffuser; SP: stripping column; SP + T: stripping column with MEC operated at 30 °C.

current density, the corresponding cathodic Faradaic efficiency (Cat FE) was lower (52.4 %) compared to SP (59.1 %) (Table 2), resulting in a slightly lower H₂ production rate under the GD condition. The highest H₂ production rate was observed for the SP + T configuration, which reached 1557.6 ± 233.1 LH₂ m⁻³ reactor d⁻¹, consistent with the highest current density. This configuration also demonstrated the highest Cat FE (64.5 %), however, this improvement cannot be solely attributed to the temperature effect. Theoretically, Cat FE, defined as the ratio between the moles of H₂ gas produced and the total electrons received at the cathode, was expected to approach 100 %, as no competing parasitic reactions are expected at the cathode that would interfere with the hydrogen evolution reaction. However, measured H₂ concentrations in the gas averaged around 60 %, with main impurities being N₂, O₂ and trace amounts of CO₂ and CH₄. The reduced Cat FE values are likely attributable to engineering limitations in the reactor, such as gas leakage, H₂ membrane crossover and atmospheric contamination during gas sampling and analysis, due to the manual method, with considerable uncertainty, described above. According to the current density of each configuration and Cat FE of 100 %, the potential maximum H₂ production rates were calculated to be 1719.9, 1564.0 and 2409.1 LH₂ m⁻³ reactor d⁻¹ for GD, SP and SP + T, respectively.

The H₂ production rates achieved in the present study are within the range reported in the literature for laboratory-scale MEC systems, generally spanning from 1000 to 10,000 LH₂ m⁻³ reactor d⁻¹ (Park et al., 2022). Notably, the MEC employed herein is a medium-scale system, with an electrode surface area of 100 cm². This prolonged and stable performance under continuous operation conditions highlights the robustness and scalability potential of the system beyond conventional short-term laboratory experiments.

Regarding the energy performance, SEC_{H₂} values were 38.4 ± 1.2, 34.4 ± 3.9 and 31.4 ± 2.9 kWh kg⁻¹ H₂ for GD, SP and SP + T, respectively (Fig. 4). The SP + T configuration demonstrated the lowest SEC_{H₂}, indicating superior energy efficiency. Considering the lower heating value of hydrogen (33.3 kWh kg⁻¹ H₂), the specific energy efficiencies of all three MEC configurations were near or exceeded 100 %, significantly surpassing those of conventional water electrolysis systems, which typically range from 55–65 % (>55 kWh kg⁻¹ H₂). This high energy yield in MEC arises from the fact that H₂ is not generated via the reverse of its combustion reaction, oxidation of water in the anode performing the oxygen evolution reaction. Instead, MECs utilize both electrical energy and the chemical energy released from the oxidation of organic matter at the bioanode, leading to energy conversion efficiencies greater than 100 % (Cheng and Logan, 2007; Pérez-Pi et al., 2024; Rabaey and Rozendal, 2010).

3.3. COD removal assessment

The performance of the MEC reactor in terms of organic matter degradation was evaluated under batch operation mode as described above. The system was fed with synthetic wastewater containing COD and NH₄⁺ and to ensure that NH₄⁺ removal and recovery were not limited by substrate availability, COD was maintained in excess throughout all experimental cycles. As a result, COD removal (COD_{rem}) efficiencies were limited and ranged from 50 % to 60 % across all operational modes (Table 2), although higher removal percentages could be achieved with extended batch durations. While the overall COD_{rem} rates across configurations remained relatively similar, this is likely due to the contribution of organic matter degradation occurring in the unheated external buffer tank, which is common to all three configurations and not thermally controlled.

The organic removal rates (ORR) achieved were 0.7 ± 0.1, 0.9 ± 0.1 and 1.2 ± 0.1 kg_{COD} m⁻³ d⁻¹ for the GD, SP and SP + T configurations, respectively. The slightly enhanced performance observed under the SP + T condition could be attributed to the operational temperature of 30 °C, which may promote microbial activity and electrochemical reactions. These ORR values are consistent with those reported by

Heidrich et al. for MEC systems, which range from 0.1 to 1.06 kgCOD m⁻³ d⁻¹ (Cotterill et al., 2017; Leicester et al., 2020; Ramírez-Moreno et al., 2019) and are also comparable to the performance of conventional activated sludge systems (0.6–2.0 kgBOD₅ m⁻³ d⁻¹) (Leicester et al., 2020)).

The specific energy consumption for COD removal (SEC_{COD}) was assessed across the three tested configurations, yielding values in the narrow range of 0.11 to 0.17 kWh kgCOD⁻¹, with small variation among them (Table 2). Although the SP + T configuration exhibited a higher overall energy demand, attributable to increased current density, it simultaneously achieved a marginally higher ORR. These opposing effects balanced each other, resulting in a SEC_{COD} value comparable to those observed under GD and SP conditions. The energy performance of the MEC reported in this study shows strong competitive potential when benchmarked against conventional wastewater treatment technologies. Reported electricity consumption for urban WWTPs ranges between 0.85 and 3.2 kWh kgCOD⁻¹ (Vaccari et al., 2018), or, for example, conventional activated sludge processes requires between 0.5 and 2 kWh kgCOD⁻¹. In terms of MEC technology, the energy requirements, reported in literature, span a wider range, from as low as 0.15 up to 7.0 kWh kgCOD⁻¹, depending on system design and operational conditions (Leicester et al., 2020).

Anodic CE is defined as the ratio of electrons recovered as electrical current relative to the total electrons theoretically available from the oxidation of organic matter in the anolyte. The An CE values obtained in this study were consistent with previously reported ranges (de Fouchécour et al., 2022), though no clear trend was observed across the tested operational modes, reaching 67.6 ± 21.3 %, 44.9 ± 2.5 %, 59.0 ± 9.1 % for GD, SP and SP + T respectively. The degradation of organic matter in the buffer tank by planktonic microorganisms, rather than those in the anodic biofilm, reduces the fraction of electrons that can be recovered at the anode, thus decreasing the An CE. Finally, organic matter degradation (COD_{rem}) was 52.1 % ± 0.7 %, 50.5 % ± 2.2 % and 58.1 % ± 10.6 %, for GD, SP and SP + T respectively, also showing a similar degradation under all the operational modes. These variabilities and the lack of clear impact of the three operational configurations on An CE and COD_{rem}, may be explained by the fact that the anolyte was fed with an excess of organic matter so as not to limit the performance of the reactor.

3.4. Ammonium recovery dynamics in extended MEC operation

A long cycle (180 h) was conducted to evaluate the performance of the MEC system for continuous *N*-NH₄⁺ removal and recovery, without replacing the catholyte nor the extraction solution. The anolyte was refreshed every 45 h, thereby avoiding limitations associated with organic matter or NH₄⁺ depletion in the anodic chamber. As shown in Fig. 5 and Table S 5, the temporal evolution of pH and NH₄⁺ concentration reflects the progressive neutralization of a 0.25 M H₂SO₄ solution in the extraction tank by cathodically produced NH₃. The pH profile exhibits characteristic sigmoidal behavior, indicative of a titration-like neutralization process. During the initial 80 h, the solution remained highly acidic (pH < 2), attributed to the high proton concentration in the sulfuric acid medium. After 100 h, a pronounced increase in pH was observed, coinciding with an NH₄⁺/SO₄²⁻ molar ratio approaching 2, which aligns with the theoretical stoichiometry of sulfuric acid neutralization, where each H₂SO₄ molecule requires two NH₃ molecules for complete neutralization. The pH subsequently stabilized between 10 and 11, indicating near-complete neutralization and a slight excess of NH₄⁺. In parallel, NH₄⁺ concentration (red dotted line) increased steadily, reaching over 12,000 mgN L⁻¹ at 180 h, equivalent to approximately 3.1 gN accumulated in the extraction tank. These results confirm the feasibility of using biogenically produced ammonia for the generation of ammonium sulfate solutions with tunable pH and variable NH₄⁺/SO₄²⁻ molar ratios. Furthermore, by modifying the initial H₂SO₄ concentration, the system can produce a wider spectrum of ammonium sulfate

Fig. 5. Evolution of pH (blue continuous line) and NH₄⁺ concentration (red dotted line) of long batch test. Neutralization of 0.25 M H₂SO₄ extraction solution with NH₃ produced in the cathode of MEC. MEC operated at 0.75 V with SP + T conditions. The anolyte was refreshed every 45 h, without replacing the catholyte or the extraction solution.

solutions.

The concentration of *N*-NH₄⁺ in the extraction tank shows an increase in the slope after the first 50 h of operation, with a faster accumulation rate compared to the initial phase. This shift in the NH₄⁺ accumulation profile, which reflects the *N*-NH₄⁺ recovery rate, can be attributed to the evolving concentration dynamics within the cathodic chamber. During the early stages of the cycle, the concentration of *N*-NH₄⁺ in the catholyte is relatively low. As the process continues, NH₄⁺ progressively accumulates in the cathode compartment, leading to a higher localized concentration that enhances the NH₄⁺ to NH₃ conversion. As a result, this improves the NH₃ transfer and subsequent recovery in the extraction tank. Consequently, the recovery rate of *N*-NH₄⁺ increased substantially from 26.1 gN m⁻² d⁻¹ at 45 h to 69.4 gN m⁻² d⁻¹ at 180 h (Table S 5). These insights suggest that operating the MEC in continuous mode and further research on the hydraulic retention times of catholyte and extraction solutions can potentially increase the key performance indicators as *N*-NH₄⁺ recovery rates, percentage of *N*-NH₄⁺ recovered relative to the total *N*-NH₄⁺ removed and SEC.

4. Conclusion

This study demonstrates that MECs coupled with an ammonia stripping system achieved significant ammonium recovery at low energy demand. The SP + T configuration, operated at 30 °C, achieved the highest *N*-NH₄⁺ removal (69.8 gN m⁻² d⁻¹) and recovery (37.9 gN m⁻² d⁻¹) rates, with *N*-NH₄⁺ faradaic efficiency of 74.9 % and associated SEC_N recovery of 3.3 kWh kg⁻¹N, outperforming the other configurations tested GD and SP, which were operated at 20–25 °C. H₂ production was maximized at 1557.6 LH₂ m⁻³ d⁻¹, with significantly high energy efficiencies. The specific energy consumption for COD removal yielded values in the range of 0.11 to 0.17 kWh kgCOD⁻¹ while allowing organic removal rates comparable to those previously reported, offering an energy efficient technology for water treatment. The tested system demonstrated the feasibility of using biogenically produced ammonia for the generation of ammonium sulfate solutions with tunable pH and variable NH₄⁺/SO₄²⁻ molar ratios. Overall, MEC-driven ammonium sulfate production demonstrates a sustainable, energy-efficient approach that integrates effective wastewater treatment with the recovery of value-added products, including hydrogen and ammonium salts, supporting circular economy principles.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the author(s) used ChatGPT and M365 Copilot to improve the clarity, structure of phrases, grammar and orthography while technical content is preserved. After using these tools/services, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed, taking and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the published article.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jorge Luque-Rueda: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Pau Bosch-Jimenez:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Martí Aliaguilla:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation. **Daniele Molognoni:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Eduard Borràs Camps:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2025.133854>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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